

A Novel Route to the Synthesis of 3-Arylimino-5-*p*-Methoxyphenyl-1,2,4-Dithiazoles. Part—III

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The synthesis of a series of a new 3-arylimino-5-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles (IV) has been described by the oxidative debenylation and cyclisation of *S*-benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamide (II) with bromine in concentrated chloroform solution. The structure of these dithiazoles (IV) has been confirmed by their comparison with the compounds obtained by the direct oxidation of the corresponding *N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamide (III).

A couple of methods have been used for the synthesis of substituted 1,2,4-dithiazoles^{1,2}. Earlier, we reported the synthesis of some of these heterocycles^{3,4} by the interaction of thiocarbamoylthioamides with bromine. Here we report the synthesis of some new *S*-benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamides and their elaboration to certain novel heterocycles i.e., 3-arylimino-5-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles.

The thiohydrolysis of *p*-methoxybenzimidazole afforded *p*-methoxythiobenzamide, which was benzylated with benzylchloride in presence of sodium methoxide. The resulting *S*-benzyliso-*p*-methoxythiobenzamide was subjected to reaction with appropriate arylisothiocyanate to yield the corresponding *S*-benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamide (II). The chloroform solution of the latter was treated with bromine, when the benzyl group was eliminated as benzylbromide followed by ring closure to the related 3-arylimino-5-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles (IV). These dithiazoles have also been obtained by the oxidation of the corresponding *N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamide (III), which were obtained by the reductive debenylation of the related *S*-benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamide (II) with hydrogen sulphide in pyridine-triethylamine⁴ and also by reduction of IV under identical conditions. The structural assignments of the compounds III and IV were rationalized by their synthesis through alternative routes as described above.

The IR spectra of compounds II and III showed characteristic absorption in the region around 3150-3400 cm⁻¹ and 1470-1500 cm⁻¹ indicating -NH stretching^{5,6} and -N-C(=S)-N- grouping⁶, respectively. A weak absorption in the region 1600-1640 cm⁻¹ and strong absorption at 1250 cm⁻¹ were recorded due to -NH⁶ and -C-NH.Ar⁶ deformation vibration of compounds II and III. In compounds III, the absorption at 1370 cm⁻¹

showed the presence of -C=S grouping⁷⁻¹⁰. The compounds IV were characterised by the absorption appearing at 1620 cm⁻¹ (-C=N- grouping)⁷⁻⁸, 1350-1500 cm⁻¹ (ring -C-S- stretching)⁷ and 480-510 cm⁻¹ (-S-S- linkage)^{7,8}, respectively. The scheme of the reactions can be outlined as given on next page.

Experimental

Melting points of all the compounds are taken by open capillary tube method and are uncorrected. IR spectra were run in Nujol on Perkin-Elmer model 720-Infrared spectrophotometer. *p*-Methoxythiobenzamide was prepared according to known methods.

S-Benzylisothiobenzamide (I) : *p*-Methoxythiobenzamide (5 g; 0.03 mole) was benzylated with benzylchloride (3.75 g, 3.4 ml; 0.03 mole) in presence of sodium methoxide (1.61 g; 0.03 mole) using methanol (25 ml) as solvent. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 hr with gentle heating and was allowed to stand overnight. It was refluxed for 15 min. Solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with benzene and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. The evaporation of excess benzene gave the expected *S*-benzyliso-*p*-methoxythiobenzamide, yield 4.0 g (52%), crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 130°.

S-Benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamides (II) (Ar=C₆H₅): The details of a typical experiment are given below. *S*-Benzyliso-*p*-methoxythiobenzamide (5 g; 0.019 mole) was refluxed with phenylisothiocyanate (2.62 g; 0.019 mole) and 30 ml of 10% sodium hydroxide solution for 2 hr. The resulting mixture was extracted with benzene and the benzene extract was further heated under reflux for 1 hr. After evaporation of excess of benzene, the resulting mass was washed with petroleum ether (40-60°) and a little ethanol added

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and were found to be identical with the respective 3-arylimino-5-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles (Table 2). The identity was confirmed from undepressed m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra.

N-Arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamides (III) :

(i) *Reductive debenylation of S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-p-methoxythiobenzamides (II)* : The reductive debenylation of *S*-benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamides (II) was carried out by dissolving these in a mixture of pyridine-triethylamine (1 : 6) and passing a stream of dry hydrogen sulphide for 4 hr. The reaction mixtures, on pouring over crushed ice and acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid, afforded the related *N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamides (III) which were filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The results are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—*N*-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-*p*-METHOXYTHIOBENZAMIDES (III)

Ar	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield (%)	Analysis	
				Calcd.	Found
<i>C</i> ₆ <i>H</i> ₅ -	<i>C</i> ₁₅ <i>H</i> ₁₄ <i>N</i> ₂ <i>S</i> ₂	150	72	C, 59.60 H, 04.69	60.13 04.87
<i>p</i> - <i>H</i> ₃ <i>CC</i> ₆ <i>H</i> ₄ -	<i>C</i> ₁₆ <i>H</i> ₁₆ <i>N</i> ₂ <i>S</i> ₂	145	75	C, 60.75 H, 05.06	60.47 04.89
<i>p</i> - <i>ClC</i> ₆ <i>H</i> ₄ -	<i>C</i> ₁₅ <i>H</i> ₁₃ <i>N</i> ₂ <i>S</i> ₂ <i>Cl</i>	180	69	C, 59.49 H, 03.86	53.53 03.89
<i>p</i> - <i>MeOC</i> ₆ <i>H</i> ₄ -	<i>C</i> ₁₆ <i>H</i> ₁₆ <i>N</i> ₂ <i>S</i> ₂ <i>O</i>	165	68	C, 57.88 H, 04.81	57.85 04.97
<i>p</i> - <i>EtOC</i> ₆ <i>H</i> ₄ -	<i>C</i> ₁₇ <i>H</i> ₁₈ <i>N</i> ₂ <i>S</i> ₂ <i>O</i>	170	68	C, 58.95 H, 05.20	59.02 05.31

(ii) *Reduction of 3-arylimino-5-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles (IV) with hydrogen sulphide in pyridine-triethylamine solution* : The related dithiazoles (IV) were dissolved in a mixture of pyridine-triethylamine and were reduced by passing a stream of dry hydrogen sulphide for about 2 hr. The

expected *N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamides (III) were obtained on pouring the reaction mixture over crushed ice followed by acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid, which were crystallised from ethanol. The identity of each product was established by m.m.p. with authentic samples obtained by the conventional reduction of *S*-benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-*p*-methoxythiobenzamides and also by identical ir spectra.

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